

What are we going to do about PURL?

Paul Walk

Founder and Director, Antleaf
Managing Director, DCMI

Web: <http://www.paulwalk.net>
Email: paul@paulwalk.net

<http://purl.org/dc/terms/>

ENDANGERED SPECIES

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